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後蘇哈托時期印尼華人之參政：
以參選地方首長爭取當地社會對於華人之認同

Indonesian Tionghoa's Political Participation in Post-Soeharto Era:

The Strive for Identity from Local Societies

by Running for Elections of Local Chief Executives

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摘要

2014年，印尼出現後蘇哈托時期首位華人省長—鍾萬學，不僅象徵印尼華人之參政邁向新里程碑，激勵更多華人投入當地政治事務，亦有助於維繫華人地位與權利。然而回顧蘇哈托下野之後的印尼華人的參政，不論是華人自組政黨參與當地政治事務，或是代表主流政黨參與議會或地方選舉，當地社會仍有部分不認同華人身份與其族群參政之反對聲音。相較於印尼華人社會，近年積極呼籲與尋求族群自我認同，華人亦須努力爭取當地社會對於華人之認同，透過民主體制之參政途徑，漸次達成其他層面之認同。

本文首先透過後蘇哈托時期，印尼華人參政事實之文獻分析，認為投身地方首長選舉已漸為華人參政趨勢；並藉由鍾萬學之參政過程與作為，奠定對於華人參政之指標意義。其次，以網路民族誌作為資料蒐集之方法，觀察當地社會對於鍾萬學華人身份之特定議題的留言，可發現多元而一體之國家意識已漸入人心，因而多數人能接受華人身為國家公民，參與當地政治。

是故，本文認為華人參政不單只為維繫華人社會之生存與發展，反而是得以爭取當地社會對於華人之認同的切入點。儘管當前印尼華人之參政，仍須面臨內外部之窒礙，並積極耕耘於當地政治領域；不過隨著華人參政之勢漸盛，不僅能向內凝聚其自我認同，透過參政促進之交流與互動，亦有助於獲得當地社會對於華人之認同。因此本文提出以華人參政作為切入點，爭取當地社會對於華人之認同的探索性途徑；透過此途徑促進彼此互動，有助於雙方達到其他層面之認同，進而體現印尼建國五原則與多元而一體之國家基礎。

關鍵字：印尼華人、華人參政、鍾萬學、印尼社會之認同、地方首長、
多元而一體、網路民族誌

Abstract

In 2014, Basuki Cahaya Purnama (popularly known as Ahok) was inaugurated as the first governor with Tionghoa ethnicity in the post-Soeharto era. His case not only marks the milestone of Tionghoa's political participation in Indonesia, but also inspires more Tionghoa to engage in the local politics, with the aim of maintaining their social status and rights. Nevertheless, while Tionghoa enthusiastically participate in the local politics by means of establishing political parties, being upheld by mainstream parties for representative elections, or running for local elections, there are still some people in the public who do not recognize Tionghoa's identity and their political participation. Therefore, with companion of recent advocacy to strive for self-identity, the Indonesian-Tionghoa can leap at the chance, through the approach of political participation in the democratic electoral system, to gain the preliminary identity from local society, and gradually achieve identity in other aspects.

By analyzing the facts of Indonesian-Tionghoa's political participation after the fall of Soeharto, this research firstly shows that running for elections of local chief executives has steadily become the trend for Tionghoa's political participation. Moreover, with netnography as the method of data collecting for further analysis, the ideology of *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika* (Unity in Diversity) has been rooted in the public's mind since several significant cases, discriminating Basuki's Tionghoa identity, are denounced by most people in their comments. Accordingly, more people in Indonesia can also accept Tionghoa, as national citizens, to engage in local politics.

Therefore, it is shown in these case analyses that Tionghoa's political participation is not only the way to sustain their development, but also the entry point to obtain identity from the local public. Although Tionghoa still need to be more

active in political participation with facing internal and external hampers, they may be benefited from interaction brought by more Tionghoa's political participation, which enhances both their self-identity bound and the identity from the society.

To sum up, this exploratory research concludes that Indonesian-Tionghoa should seize the opportunity to strive for identity from the public by political participation, which gives Tionghoa a potential approach to stimulating their interaction with the local public and other dimensions of identity from the latter, so as to embody the values disclosed in the national ideology, Pancasila and Bhinneka Tunggal Ika.

Keywords: Indonesian-Tionghoa (Chinese), political participation of Tionghoa (Chinese), Basuki Cahaya Purnama (Ahok), identity from Indonesian society, local chief executives, Bhinneka Tunggal Ika, netnography

Kata Kunci: Tionghoa-Indonesia, Partisipasi Politik Warga Tionghoa-Indonesia, Basuki Cahaya Purnama (Ahok), identitas dari masyarakat local, kepala pemerintah daerah, Bhinneka Tunggal Ika, netnografi

目錄

謝辭.....	I
中文摘要.....	III
英文摘要 (Abstract)	V
目錄.....	VII
圖目錄.....	XI
表目錄.....	XIII
第壹章 緒論.....	1
第一節、研究動機	1
第二節、問題意識	4
第三節、研究目的	4
第貳章 文獻探討與理論回顧	5
第一節、文獻探討	5
一、後蘇哈托時期印尼華人的政治參與	5
二、後蘇哈托時期印尼華人與當地族群之關係與互動	16
三、本文研究於現有文獻之重要性	23
第二節、理論回顧	24
一、華人參政與其途徑	24
二、自我認同與外部認同	25
第三節、本文之研究理論與相關概念	29

第參章 研究方法與架構	31
第一節、研究方法	31
一、研究內容分析方法	31
二、文獻與資料蒐集方法	32
三、本文研究使用之文獻與資料	38
第二節、研究架構與範圍	39
一、研究架構	39
二、研究範圍	40
第肆章 後蘇哈托時期印尼華人之政治參與	41
第一節、印尼華人政黨之發展已式微	41
第二節、委任政府要職的印尼華人	45
第三節、華人尋求主流政黨支持參選各級議員	46
第四節、投身地方首長選舉漸為華人參政趨勢	48
一、成功勝選之印尼華人	48
二、未能勝選之印尼華人	52
第五節、從華人政黨到投身地方首長選舉	54
第伍章 鍾萬學與當前華人參政趨勢及困難	57
第一節、長期投入印尼政治領域的鍾萬學	57
第二節、鍾萬學對於印尼華人參政之指標意義	61
一、挑戰既有政治生態	61
二、突破少數族群之身份限制從政	63
三、奠定當前華人參政趨勢	65

第三節、探究當前投身地方首長選舉之參政趨勢	66
第四節、當前印尼華人參政之困難與窒礙	72
一、內部困難	72
二、外部窒礙	73
第陸章 透過參政爭取印尼社會對於華人之認同	75
第一節、觀察當地社會對於印尼華人參政之反應與認同	75
一、負面反應	75
二、正面認同	83
第二節、參政對於印尼華人自我認同之潛在影響	94
第三節、以華人參政為切入點試探印尼社會對於華人之認同	98
第柒章 結論.....	105
第一節、研究結果與發現	105
第二節、研究建議與未來展望	108
參考文獻.....	111
一、中文	111
二、英文	124
三、印尼文	137
四、其他語文	153
附錄一：案例留言原文	155
附錄二：中印名稱翻譯一覽表	171

圖目錄

圖3.1	本文研究分析架構圖.....	40
圖6.1	選民對於有意參選2017年雅加達省長者之支持度比較.....	88
圖6.2	以參政為切入點試探當地社會對於華人之認同示意圖.....	103

表目錄

表2.1	其他與印尼華人參與議題相關之文獻分析.....	8
表2.2	針對印尼華人與當地社會互動之其他文獻分析.....	21
表2.3	萬曉宏的當代加拿大華人參政模型.....	25
表3.1	本研究議題案例之簡要介紹與留言來源.....	37
表4.1	參選及當選人民代表會議議員（DPR）之印尼華人人數.....	46
表4.2	印尼華人參政模型之特徵分析.....	55
表5.1	部分勝選地方首長之華人與當地族群或宗教人口比例.....	68
表5.2	後蘇哈托時期印尼華人參與地方首長選舉之勝敗分析.....	70
表6.1	歧視鍾萬學華人身份之發言與網友留言－案例一.....	78
表6.2	歧視鍾萬學華人身份之發言與網友留言－案例二.....	79
表6.3	歧視鍾萬學華人身份之發言與網友留言－案例三.....	81
表6.4	鍾萬學擔任省長一年多之施政滿意度調查結果.....	84
表6.5	歧視華人族群與鍾萬學之發言與網友留言－案例四.....	86
表6.6	歧視鍾萬學華人身份之發言與網友評論－案例五.....	89
表6.7	歧視鍾萬學華人身份之發言與網友留言－案例六.....	91
表6.8	歧視鍾萬學華人身份之發言與網友留言－案例七.....	96
表6.9	雅加達省民眾對於政治人物族群身份之態度調查.....	100
表6.10	2016年六月底印尼調查圈針對鍾萬學支持者之族群比例.....	101

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